

OXALATO-MOLYBDATES OF SOME COMPLEX METALLIC CATIONS

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The reaction between acid ammonium mono-oxalatomolybdate and complex cobalt cations in aqueous solution gave products of the general formula, $R_x(NH_4)_y [MoO_3(C_2O_4)_z] \cdot xH_2O$, where R is a complex cation like $[Co(BigH^+)_3]^{3+}$, $[Co. En_3]^{3+}$, $[Co(NH_3)_6]^{3+}$; BigH = $C_2N_5H_7$, one molecule of biguanide; En = $C_2N_2H_8$, one molecule of ethylenediamine; x, y, and z are certain specified integral numbers. In the case of cobaltic trisbiguanide compound y=0, and hence only one type (normal) of salt was obtained. The composition and dehydration of these compounds furnish evidences regarding the stability of the anionic complex mono-oxalatomolybdate in aqueous solution.

The complex oxalatomolybdates of some simple metallic cations and organic bases, as well as the free complex acids in certain cases, have been studied by different workers (Pechard, *Compt. rend.*, 1889, 108, 1052; Rosenheim, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1893, 4, 352, 362; 1896, 11, 228; *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1192; Rosenheim and Berthelm, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 34, 427, 436; Rosenheim and Weinheber, *ibid.*, 1911, 69, 263; Spittle and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1748).

The oxalato-molybdates have been found to belong to three classes represented by

where R=H or any univalent cation and B=an organic base. Their constitution have been discussed by Rosenheim and his co-workers as well as by Spittle and Wardlaw.

In the present paper some complex cobaltamine mono-oxalatomolybdates have been described. Their composition supports the view that the molybdc and oxalic acids combine to form a complex anionic entity with hexa-co-ordinated and sexivalent molybdenum as the central atom and that this complex anion is also stable in solution. Otherwise, the sparingly soluble oxalate of the complex cations would have been precipitated from the solution along with some polymolybdates. With cobaltic trisbiguanide chloride it gave only the normal salt, while with ethylenediamine cobaltic chloride and hexammine cobaltic nitrate it gave double ammonium salts with variable ammonia content. Some of these compounds lost all their water-content at about 80° and even the acid ammonium mono-oxalatomolybdate prepared by us contained only 1/2 mol. of H₂O, showing that this complex anion should be represented as $[MoO_3(C_2O_4)]^{6-}$ and not as an aquo-mono-oxalatomolybdate, $[H_2O \cdot MoO_3(C_2O_4)]^{6-}$ formulated by some previous workers.

Two of the three oxygen atoms in this complex anion, therefore, occupy one co-ordination position each in an octahedral configuration with the possibility for the complex to exist in *cis* and *trans* isomeric forms as shown below. Of these again the *cis*-form will be resolvable into its optical antipodes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acid Ammonium Mono-oxalatomolybdate.—The substance was prepared according to Rosenheim's method. It gave on analysis the following results :

{Found: Mo, 36.88; C₂O₄, 33.70. (NH₄)H[MoO₃(C₂O₄)] · 0.5H₂O requires Mo, 36.92; C₂O₄, 33.85 per cent.}

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Mono-oxalatomolybdate.—A concentrated solution of acid ammonium mono-oxalatomolybdate (1g.) was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a solution of cobaltic trisbiguanide chloride (2g.). A reddish brown precipitate separated out. The product was filtered, washed free from chloride with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. It was finally dried in air. {Found: N, 27'87; Co, 7'86; Mo, 19'22; C₂O₄, 17'52. [Co(BigH⁺)₃]₂ [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₃]₃, 4H₂O requires N, 28'15; Co, 7'91; Mo, 19'30; C₂O₄, 17'68 per cent}.

A second sample on analysis gave N, 27'67; Co, 7'66; Mo, 19'03; C₂O₄, 17'46; H₂O (by loss at 80°), 7'20. [Co(BigH⁺)₃]₂ [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₃]₃, 6H₂O requires N, 27'48; Co, 7'72; Mo, 18'84; C₂O₄, 17'28; H₂O, 7'07 per cent.

Hexammine Cobaltic Ammonium Mono-oxalatomolybdate.—(a) A solution of acid ammonium mono-oxalatomolybdate (<1 mol.) in water was added, drop by drop with constant stirring, to that of an excess of hexammine cobaltic nitrate (> 2/3 mol.). A yellowish brown precipitate appeared at once. This was allowed to settle, and then washed and dried as above.

{Found: N, 14'83; Co, 8'85; Mo, 28'91; C₂O₄, 26'06; H₂O (by loss at 80°) 4'05. [Co(NH₃)₆](NH₄) [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₂]₂, 1'5H₂O requires N, 14'62; Co, 8'81; Mo, 28'65; C₂O₄, 26'26; H₂O, 4'03 per cent}.

(b) When, however, a solution of hexammine cobaltic nitrate (1g.) in water was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a solution of an excess of ammonium acid mono-oxalatomolybdate (2g.) a light yellow precipitate of different composition was obtained. This was washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 12'55; Co, 5'84; Mo, 28'89; C₂O₄, 26'27; H₂O (by loss at 110°) 8'68. [Co(NH₃)₆](NH₄)₃ [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₃]₃, 5H₂O requires N, 12'59; Co, 5'90; Mo, 28'77; C₂O₄, 26'37; H₂O, 8'99 per cent}.

trisEthylenediamine Cobaltic Ammonium Mono-oxalatomolybdate.—(a) A pale yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained from a concentrated solution of acid ammonium mono-oxalatomolybdate (1g.) and an excess of a dilute solution of trisethylenediamine cobaltic chloride (1'1 g.) as described in the previous preparations. {Found: N, 12'34; Co, 6'76; Mo, 25'28; C₂O₄, 23'0; H₂O (by loss at 80°), 8'16. [Co. En₃]₃ (NH₄)₃ [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₃]₃, 12H₂O requires N, 12'17; Co, 6'69; Mo, 25'39; C₂O₄, 23'28; H₂O, 8'16 per cent}.

(b) A compound of different composition was obtained when a concentrated solution of trisethylenediamine cobaltic chloride (1g.) was added to that of an ammonium hydrogen mono-oxalatomolybdate in excess (2g.). The substance forms pale yellow beautiful crystals, sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 12'34; Co, 6'19; Mo, 27'46; C₂O₄, 24'60. [Co. En₃]₃ (NH₄)₃ [MoO₃(C₂O₄)₃]₃, 9H₂O requires N, 12'23; Co, 6'19; Mo, 26'84; C₂O₄, 24'66 per cent}.